

Delft University of Technology

Morphodynamic modeling of sediment augmentation in rivers

*The feasibility of reduced flow equations for long-term
morphodynamic modeling of sediment augmentation in
lowland rivers*

Bachelor thesis

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Preface

It is not even two months ago that I started working on this bachelor thesis. It is the final step in finishing my bachelors in Civil Engineering, but it is also a step towards my MSc in Hydraulic Engineering at Delft University of Technology.

During the eight weeks that I worked on this topic, I learned so much about river morphodynamics that I cannot imagine anymore that the first few days of these eight weeks were only about following lectures on river engineering. Also, I enjoyed working on and using a complicated numerical model in Matlab, whereas I had never worked with this software before. So I am glad to finish my bachelor thesis project with the results in this report, but above all I am glad that I learned so much during this short period of time.

I am grateful to my supervisors, Astrid Blom and Liselot Arkesteijn, for their support and comments on my work and this report. Furthermore, I would like to thank Liselot Arkesteijn and Victor Chavarrias for their help with using the numerical model they developed.

Now this report is finished, I am looking forward to start my masters in September – mainly because I explored so many things I want to know more about. I hope you enjoy reading this report.

Roy van Weerdenburg

June 12th, Delft

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Abstract

Sediment augmentation is a measure to stabilize the river bed and to stop the erosion of sediment from the river bed. Morphodynamic modelling is recommended to investigate the morphodynamic adjustments induced by sediment augmentation. Highly accurate predictions of the morphodynamic behavior after sediment augmentation result in high computational costs. Therefore, it is interesting to consider how accurate predictions based on a simplified modeling approach are.

This study predicts the morphodynamic adjustments induced by sediment augmentation by simulations based on five different flow models. The most complicated flow model is based on the one-dimensional Saint-Venant equations. The other four flow models are based on reduced flow equations and consider the flow as quasi-steady, alternating steady or steady. Two alternating steady flow models are distinguished, one with 20 modes and one with 3 modes. The response to sediment augmentation is investigated in two situations. In the first situation, the river bed and the supplied sediment consist of unisize sediment. The second situation deals with a mixture of sand and gravel.

In simulations, sediment augmentation takes place over a section of 1000 m and causes a disturbance from the equilibrium profile. This disturbance propagates downstream while it deforms. The considered domain has a length of 100 km. In a unisize river bed, sediment augmentation induces one single wave in the river bed, whereas it induces two waves in a mixed sediment river bed. The slowest propagating wave of these two is much coarser than the other.

It follows from the results of this study that the propagation velocity of the disturbances are highly accurately predicted by an alternating steady flow model with 20 modes. A prediction of the travelled distance in a period of 10 years deviates not even 1 % from the prediction based on an unsteady flow model. The predictions of the deformation of the wave by this alternating steady flow model are less accurate, but still they are representative. Here, the deviation from the predictions by an unsteady flow model is only 1.6 % over the first 10 km the wave travels, but this deviation increases if the wave travels further.

The alternating steady flow model with 20 modes is used to predict the morphodynamic behavior during and after a series of sediment augmentations. The induced disturbance in the river bed by each sediment augmentation propagates downstream with a velocity approximately 5 % lower than the disturbance induced by one single sediment augmentation. 15 years after the last of the series of ten sediment augmentations took place, the predicted river bed level is still 3.9 cm above the equilibrium profile.

1. Introduction

1.1 Problem description

Although artificial sediment supply in rivers has already proved to be successful in Germany, the Netherlands are just about to start its first sediment augmentation pilot study near Lobith, where the river Rhine crosses the Dutch-German border (Gölz, 1999; Havinga, 2009). The goal of sediment augmentation in Germany was to stabilize the river bed of the Rhine between Iffezheim and Bingen (Weichert et al., 2010). The objectives of the planned sediment augmentation in the Netherlands are to stop the erosion of bed-load material and to guarantee the necessary dimensions of the fairway in 95% of the time (Havinga, 2009). For sufficient insight into the morphodynamic adjustments induced by sediment augmentation, morphodynamic modeling is recommended.

Using computational models, it is possible to predict the morphodynamic behavior after changes in the river profile. These changes can be induced by human – for example by dredging works and the construction of structures in the river bed – or by nature – by for example the change of upstream discharge or sediment supply. To get accurate predictions, a detailed and complicated computational model that represents the real situation as good as possible needs to be used. However, such an accurate model results in high computational costs. Therefore, if a more simplified modeling approach can be used, which still results in a good approximation, the computational costs may decrease.

There are different simplifications by which the unsteady behavior of a flow can be approximated. One of them is the quasi-steady approach, in which the influence of the inertia terms on the momentum balance of the flow is neglected. Therefore, in a quasi-steady approximation the driving force, which is gravity, is equal to the resistance experienced by the flow. A second approach is the alternating steady approximation, in which the discharge is considered to be constant during each time-interval. An even more simplified approach is the steady-approximation, which implies that the discharge is assumed to be constant over time and over space. The alternating steady approach distinguishes itself from the steady approach by dividing the total time into several shorter time-intervals.

The accuracy of different simplifications – distinguishing a quasi-steady, an alternating steady and a steady approximation – has already been the topic of other studies. Hummel et al. (2012) concludes that it is not known whether an alternating steady approximation is sufficiently accurate for simulating sediment transport, mainly because flood events can be rapidly varying over time and thus unsteady. Soci (2015) states that an alternating steady flow model yields a satisfying approximation of the predictions by an unsteady flow model, in the specific case of rising downstream water level.

1.2 Objectives

This study will provide insight in the way by which complicated morphodynamic models can be simplified to predict the long-term morphodynamic response to sediment augmentation. While simplifying computational models, the prediction accuracy obviously becomes lower. However, it will be investigated if simplifications can be done whereas the reduction in accuracy remains acceptable - i.e. the predictions are still representative. The main focus of this study is on the time scale at which the equilibrium state recovers and on the way by which the supplied amount of sediment is spread over the downstream region.

1.3 Research questions

The following research question is answered in this study:

How accurate are predictions of the long-term morphodynamic behavior, in response to sediment augmentation, based on simplified flow models?

This research question is subdivided into four sub-questions:

1. What are the characteristic timescales by which the artificially supplied sediment is transported downstream and what are the effects on the river profile?
2. What are the differences in timescales and effects on the river profile between the most accurate prediction and those predictions based on simplified flow models?
3. How do the adjustments in the river system change if the type of sediment changes, distinguishing unisize sediment and mixed sediment?
4. What is the long-term effect of a series of sediment measures on the river bed profile and how fast recovers the equilibrium profile?

1.4 Methodology

In order to answer the research question defined at the previous section, a literature survey is done at first. Subsequently, the input of the numerical model has to be defined in order to use the model for the simulations needed.

Chapter 2 discusses the different flow models which are used during this study. The unsteady flow equations are in this chapter reduced to a quasi-steady approach, two different alternating steady approaches and a steady approach. Soci (2015) has already defined two alternating steady approaches and two steady approaches in order to find their accuracy in predicting the morphodynamic response to sea level rise. Similar approaches will be used in this study.

Chapter 3 defines the case study of sediment augmentation in a lowland river. The quantitative as well as the qualitative properties of the sediment augmentation are based on projects which were already performed in the German part of the river Rhine and on the report of Havinga (2009) about sediment augmentation at Spijk and Lobith in the Netherlands. Chapter 3 also discusses the implementation of the case study in a numerical model by defining the initial conditions and the boundary conditions.

Chapter 4 presents the computational results of the morphodynamic response to one single sediment augmentation. These results follow from numerical computations based on five different flow models. Two different cases are considered. In the first case, the river bed as well as the artificially supplied sediment consists of unisize sediment. The second case deals with a mixture of sand and gravel. Assuming that the unsteady approach results in the best prediction of the true response of the river system, the accuracy of the simplified approaches can be determined. The most accurate approximation is used in Chapter 5 to predict the morphodynamic adjustments after a series of sediment augmentations. This series is again based on the report of Havinga (2009).

The accuracy and limitations of the results of this study are discussed in Chapter 6. Chapter 7 answers the research questions defined in the previous section and lists the conclusions of this study based on the results in Chapter 4 and Chapter 5.

2. Flow models

This study focusses on the prediction accuracy of the reduced flow models that are defined in this chapter. More theoretical background about river hydro- and morphodynamics is included in Appendix A. This appendix discusses the relations used in the current chapter, and even its derivations, more fundamentally.

2.1 Flow models

Five different flow models are distinguished in this study. Model A is the non-reduced unsteady flow model described by the Saint-Venant equations, model B is a quasi-steady flow model, both models C and D are alternating steady flow models and model E is a steady flow model.

Flow model A: Unsteady

In flow model A, the one-dimensional Saint-Venant equations are used to describe the flow. The Saint-Venant equations, given in Equations 2.1 and 2.2, are derived from respectively the conservation of mass and streamwise momentum of the flow (Saint-Venant, 1871). More information about the physical meaning of each of the terms of those equations is included in Appendix A.

$$\frac{\partial d}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial q}{\partial s} = 0 \quad [2.1]$$

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial q^2}{\partial s d} = -gd \left(\frac{\partial d}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial s} \right) - c_f \left(\frac{q}{d} \right)^2 \quad [2.2]$$

where

- t = time [s]
- s = streamwise coordinate along the river [m]
- d = flow depth [m]
- q = water discharge per unit width [m²/s]
- z_b = bed level compared to a horizontal reference plane [m]
- c_f = friction coefficient [-]
- g = gravitational acceleration (= 9.81 m/s²) [m/s²]

Flow model B: Quasi-steady

In flow model B the flow is considered to be quasi-steady. This implies that Equation 2.2 is reduced by neglecting the inertia terms, which are the two terms on the left hand side (see also Appendix A). In general, this simplification can be applied if changes occur slowly. The hydrodynamics of the flow are then described by the following two equations:

$$\frac{\partial d}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial q}{\partial s} = 0 \quad [2.3]$$

$$gd \left(\frac{\partial d}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial s} \right) + c_f \frac{q^2}{d^2} = 0 \quad [2.4]$$

Equation 2.4 implies that the driving force balances the resistance at every location and at any time.

The flow models C, D and E consider the flow to be (alternating) steady. Appendix B pays attention to steady flow and the way in which Equations 2.1 and 2.2 are simplified.

Flow models C and D: Alternating steady

In both flow models C and D the flow is considered to be alternating steady. This assumes the discharge to be constant during each time-interval. The total time under consideration, denoted by T , is split into several time intervals dt . During each time interval dt , the discharge is assumed to be constant and the flow to be steady.

The hydrograph of an alternating steady flow model is a discretized function. Flow model C distinguishes 20 different modes of the water discharge, whereas flow model D only distinguishes 3 modes.

Flow model E: Steady

The discharge is assumed to be constant in flow model E. The backwater equation, Equation 2.5, describes the change in water depth over space in the river section. Here, i_f is the friction slope which is by definition equal to the loss of energy head over space.

$$\frac{\partial d}{\partial s} = \frac{i_b - i_f}{1 - Fr^2} \quad [2.5]$$

where $Fr^2 = \frac{q_w^2}{gd^3} = \frac{u^2}{gd}$

$$i_b = -\frac{\partial z_b}{\partial s}$$

$$i_f = c_f Fr^2$$

2.2 Convergence, consistency and stability

The numerical model used in this study has to be consistent, convergent and stable in order to generate an appropriate solution of the problem.

A numerical scheme is called convergent if the global truncation error e_{n+1} satisfies Equation 2.6:

$$\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} e_{n+1} = 0 \quad [2.6]$$

The global truncation error e_{n+1} is defined as the difference between the exact solution of the partial differential equations and the numerical approximation. If a numerical method is consistent and stable, the numerical approximation converges to the solution for $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ (Vuik et al., 2007).

A numerical method is defined consistent with the differential system if in the numerical method becomes identical with the underlying partial differential equations of the system in the limit of a small time step and a small space step (Potter, 1973).

A numerical scheme can be explicit or implicit. Fennema et al. (1986) analyse the feasibility of an explicit scheme in favour of an implicit scheme. They state that explicit schemes are easy to program and take less CPU time, defined as the amount of time a central processing unit (CPU) has spent for the computations of one time step. According to Potter (1973), the stability of an explicit computational method primarily depends on the magnitude of the time step in relation to the physical times of interest in the problem. The Von Neumann stability condition, formulated as in Equation 2.7, describes this dependency and has to be satisfied to ensure stability of the method. This condition is derived from the Courant-Friedrichs-Levy (CFL) condition, which can be applied for general hyperbolic equations (Potter, 1973).

$$\Delta t \leq \frac{\Delta s}{|v|} \quad [2.7]$$

where Δt = time step [s]

Δs = spatial step in streamwise direction [m]

v = fastest propagation velocity anywhere on the space mesh [m/s]

The order of magnitude of the fastest propagation velocity of disturbances in the river system of this study follows from Equation 2.8, which sums the flow velocity and the wave celerity in shallow water:

$$|v| = \frac{Q_w}{B*d} + \sqrt{g * d} \quad [2.8]$$

The order of magnitude of the flow depth during peak flow is 10m and the specific water discharge during peak flow is approximately 20 m²/s. Then it follows from Equation 2.8 that the order of magnitude of the fastest propagation velocity on the space mesh is 10 m/s. Because the spatial step in streamwise direction equals 200 m, the time step in the explicit numerical scheme must at least be smaller than 20 s.

Implicit methods are more often used in numerical models to approximate the solution of the Saint-Venant equations, because of their unconditional stability (Fennema et al., 1986). A widely applied implicit numerical method in computational flow models based on the St. Venant equations is the Preissmann box scheme. This scheme approximates the differential system in Equation 2.9 by the expressions in Equations 2.10a and 2.10b (Cunge & Verwey, 1990):

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial G(f)}{\partial x} = 0 \quad [2.9]$$

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \approx \frac{(f_{j+1}^{n+1} + f_j^{n+1}) - (f_{j+1}^n + f_j^n)}{2\Delta t} \quad [2.10a]$$

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \approx \frac{\theta(G_{j+1}^{n+1} - f_j^{n+1}) + (1-\theta)(G_{j+1}^n - G_j^n)}{\Delta x} \quad [2.10b]$$

Preissmann's scheme is unconditionally stable if the weighting parameter θ satisfies Equation 2.11 (Samuels & Skeels, 1990):

$$\theta \geq \frac{1}{2} \quad [2.11]$$

The unsteady and quasi-steady simulations in this study use the implicit Preissman scheme and a time step of 180 s to approximate the solution of the one-dimensional Saint-Venant equations. Cunge & Verwey (1990) describe the application of the Preissmann scheme to the derivatives in the Saint-Venant equations in detail. The values of the weighting parameter for unsteady and quasi-steady simulations are respectively $\theta = 1$ and $\theta = \frac{1}{2}$.

3. Case study

This chapter defines the characteristic parameters of the river section in which sediment augmentation takes place, based on the characteristic parameters of the Dutch Rhine. Furthermore, this chapter discusses the boundary conditions, the initial conditions and the occurrence of a hydrograph boundary layer.

The river section under consideration in this study is straight, it has a prismatic cross-section and it is located in a lowland region. The width of the channel is constant. Two different situations are part of this study. The first situation simplifies the sediment in the river to unisize sediment. This implies the Exner equation describes the conservation of sediment mass. The typical grain size of the sediment is equal to 0.9 mm (very coarse sand). The porosity of this sediment is equal to 0.3 and the dimensionless friction coefficient is equal to 0.004. The total friction is assumed equal to the skin friction. All parameters are summarized in Table 3.1.

PARAMETERS	VALUES
River width, B	250 m
Uniform bed grain size, D	$0.9 * 10^{-3}$ m
Friction coefficient, c_f	0.004
Porosity, p	0.3

Table 3.1: Parameters unisize sediment model

In the second situation, the active layer model of Hirano (1971) describes the morphodynamic response of a river bed consisting of two different types of grains – i.e. very coarse sand and fine gravel. The grain size of the sand is $D_{sand} = 0.9$ mm and of the gravel is $D_{gravel} = 5.0$ mm. Although the size of the gravel grains is outside the experimental range of Engelund and Hansen (1967), their relation, as described in Appendix A, will still be used. The dimensionless friction coefficient is again equal to $c_f = 0.004$. The thickness of the active layer is 1.0 m and the grain size distribution of the artificially supplied sediment is equal to that in the active layer at the moment of sediment augmentation.

PARAMETERS	VALUES
River width, B	250 m
Very coarse sand, D_{sand}	$0.9 * 10^{-3}$ m
Fine gravel, D_{gravel}	$5.0 * 10^{-3}$ m
Friction coefficient, c_f	0.004
Porosity, p	0.3
Active layer thickness, L_a	0.5 m

Table 3.2: Parameters mixed sediment model

3.1 Case study

Both river sections upstream and downstream of the location where sediment augmentation takes place are considered in numerical computations. Although the main focus is on the downstream effects, this ensures that the propagation of the disturbance to river sections further upstream is predicted. In this study, sediment augmentation takes place over a length of 1000 m and the increase in river bed level over this length equals 0.50 m. The height of the augmentation is constant over the width of the river.

The long-term morphodynamic adjustments are considered in a river section of 100 km, in which sediment augmentation takes place 75 km from upstream. It induces a disturbance from the equilibrium situation. Although this study focusses on the long term response, the short term response to this disturbance is quickly considered in this section. In the case of constant discharge (flow model E), the equilibrium bed slope is constant over the entire domain. Sediment augmentations induces an increase in bed elevation of

0.5 m over a section of 1000 m, whereas the normal flow depth stays the same. The initial hydrodynamic response is the occurrence of an M2 profile at the 1000 m where sediment augmentation takes place and an M1 profile occurs at the river section upstream. This leads to an increased flow velocity over the section of the augmentation and a decreased flow velocity just upstream of it. Figure 3.1 shows the initial hydrodynamic response in a river section with constant discharge (flow model E) graphically.

Figure 3.1: Initial hydrodynamic response to sediment augmentation for steady flow

How and at which timescale adjustments take place follows from the numerical simulations, but a qualitative estimation follows from Figure 3.1. At sections with an M2 profile the flow depth decreases in streamwise direction. Therefore, the spatial change in flow velocity and thus the sediment transport rate are positive. This implies that erosion takes place at the section where sediment augmentation is applied. Upstream from this section an M1 curve occurs and here the spatial change in sediment transport rate is negative – i.e. aggradation occurs in this section.

In the case of variable flow, the discharge changes over time and therefore, because the equilibrium depth depends on the specific discharge, the equilibrium depth changes. The profile of the water surface elevation is thus dependent on the water discharge at that moment, distinguishing an M1 and an M2 profile. Appendix C shows the initial hydrodynamic response graphically in the case of variable flow (flow models A-D), during both peak flow and base flow.

3.2 Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions of the study region are the same for all years, although the upstream boundary conditions are changing during the year in case of variable flow. Because the boundary conditions are repeated every year, the river profile will, in the long term, recover to its initial equilibrium situation after sediment augmentation took place.

In the current case-study, the slope of the river is mild and the flow thus subcritical. To obtain a unique solution of the simulation, three boundary conditions are provided. An upstream and a downstream hydraulic boundary condition are needed to determine the hydrodynamic state. The third boundary condition is an upstream morphodynamic boundary condition.

Upstream boundary conditions

The upstream boundary conditions of the simulations are describing the water discharge and the sediment transport rate from upstream into the river section under consideration. These upstream boundary conditions are similar to the upstream boundary conditions in the study of Soci (2015). However, Soci held the equilibrium slope constant while modifying the unsteady discharge. In this study the annual inflow of water at the upstream end are held constant in the boundary conditions of all flow models. This section defines the hydraulic upstream boundary conditions and the morphodynamic upstream boundary conditions in the case of unisize sediment first. All five flow models are discussed. Subsequently, this section defines the morphodynamic upstream boundary condition in case the sediment consists out both sand and gravel. The hydraulic upstream boundary condition is the same for both cases.

Unisize sediment

The hydrograph of the discharge during a period of one year is shown in Figure 3.2. The base flow equals $2200 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and there are two Gauss-shaped peaks in the discharge. The highest peak reaches a water discharge of $5800 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and the lower peak a discharge of $3800 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. This hydrograph represents the hydrodynamic upstream boundary condition of flow models A and B.

Figure 3.2: Hydrograph of the discharge, the hydrodynamic upstream boundary condition of flow models A and B

In order to find the sedigraph from the hydrograph, the semi-empirical relation of Engelund-Hansen (1967) is used. This relation is discussed in Appendix A. Although the unsteady velocity at the upstream end will not be equal to the normal flow velocity, the latter will be used to relate the sedigraph to the hydrograph. The bed slope is assumed equal to 10^{-4} in order to compute the normal flow velocity with the following equation:

$$u = \left(\frac{Q i_b g}{B c_f} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad [m/s] \quad [3.1]$$

The computations result in the sedigraph in Figure 3.3. The varying sediment load is the morphodynamic upstream boundary condition of flow models A and B. The base load equals $0.0483 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, the highest peak reaches a sediment transport load of $0.2392 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and the lower peak a sediment transport load of $0.1188 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

Figure 3.3: Sedigraph, the morphodynamic upstream boundary condition of flow models A and B in case of unisize sediment

The mean values of the upstream discharge and sediment load are defined as in Equations 3.2a and 3.2b respectively.

$$E(Q_w) = \frac{\int_0^T Q_w(t) dt}{T} \quad [3.2a]$$

$$E(Q_s) = \frac{\int_0^T Q_s(t) dt}{T} \quad [3.2b]$$

It follows that $E(Q_w) = 2373 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $E(Q_s) = 0.0566 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

The alternating steady flow models C and D use discretized versions of the hydrograph in Figure 3.2 and the sedigraph in Figure 3.3, in which the number of modes is equal to 20 for flow model C and equal to 3 for flow model D. For both these flow models the hydrograph and sedigraph are modified using the following principles:

- The base flow of water and sediment are the same as in the hydrograph and sedigraph of flow model A
- The ratio between the higher peak and the lower peak above the base flow is the same as in the hydrograph and sedigraph of flow model A
- The annual inflow of water and sediment is the same as in flow model A – i.e. the mean water discharge and mean sediment transport rate coming from upstream river sections are the same
- To take into account the nonlinear relation between the water discharge and the sediment transport rate, the peaks of the sedigraph are Gaussian curves taken to the power 3/5.

This implies that the peaks of the hydrograph and the sedigraph are scaled such that the annual water and sediment discharge are equal to those for the unsteady model.

For flow model C, the lowest mode is chosen equal to the base flow of $2200 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and the highest mode is equal to the highest peak. The water discharges of the intermediate modes follow from a regular interval between these two extremes ($\Delta Q = 191$). Every value on the Gaussian curve is now chosen to be equal to the most nearby mode. The hydrograph and the sedigraph of flow model C are included in Appendix D, shown on respectively Figure D.1 and D.2. The numerical values belonging to each mode are also given in this appendix (Table D.3).

Flow model D distinguishes three different modes to describe the flow as alternating steady. Again, the peaks of the hydrograph and the sedigraph are scaled such that the mean values of the water discharge and the sediment transport load coming from upstream are equal to $E(Q_W) = 2373 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $E(Q_S) = 0.0566 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The hydrograph, the sedigraph and the corresponding values of each mode are included in respectively Figure E.1, Figure E.2 and Table E.1 in Appendix E.

Flow model E considers the flow to be steady. The water discharge is now constant and equal to the mean water discharge of the unsteady flow model, which is $E(Q_W) = 2373 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, and the sediment transport rate is constant and equal to $E(Q_S) = 0.0566 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

Mixed sediment

The upstream boundary conditions for the sand-gravel simulations are defined by the same method as for unisize sediment. The same underlying principles are used, complemented with the principle that the sediment coming from upstream consists for 80% out of sand ($D_{\text{sand}} = 0.9 \text{ mm}$) and for 20% out of gravel ($D_{\text{gravel}} = 5.0 \text{ mm}$). Again a flow velocity equal to the normal flow velocity (Equation 3.1) and a bed slope equal to $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ are assumed to relate the water discharge to the sediment load. This results in the sedigraph in Figure 3.4. This is the morphodynamic upstream boundary condition for the flow models A and B. The base load of sand is $0.0203 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and the sand load of the higher peak and the lower peak are respectively $0.1021 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $0.0505 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The mean inflow of sand at the upstream end is, according to Equation 3.2b, equal to $E(Q_{S,\text{sand}}) = 0.0238 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The base load of gravel is $0.0050 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and the peaks are reaching the values $0.0254 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $0.0125 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The mean inflow of gravel is $0.0059 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

From these values it follows that the mean total sediment inflow is $E(Q_s) = 0.0297 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. This mean sediment inflow at the upstream end is only 53% of the mean sediment inflow in case only one type of grains is present in the river bed.

In the same way as for unisize sediment, the sedigraph in Figure 3.4 is discretized to 20 modes to acquire the morphodynamic boundary condition of flow model C, and to 3 modes for flow model D. The resulting sedigraphs and the values belonging to each mode for flow models C and D are included in respectively Appendix D and Appendix E.

Figure 3.4: Sedigraph, the morphodynamic upstream boundary condition of flow models A and B in case of mixed sediment

The upstream boundary conditions for flow model E in case of mixed sediment are again constant and equal to the mean inflow of water and sediment: $E(Q_W) = 2372 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, $E(Q_{S,\text{sand}}) = 0.0238 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and $E(Q_{S,\text{gravel}}) = 0.0059 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

Downstream boundary conditions

In this study the downstream boundary condition is a fixed water level – i.e. a base level. In practice, this can for instance be the water level of the sea in which the river flows out. This base level is constant over time.

The reference level in this study is the sea level at the downstream boundary. According to the case study, the x-coordinate of this point is 100 km. Therefore, the downstream boundary condition is as follows:

$$\eta(x = 100\,000, t) = 0 \quad [m]$$

This implies that changes in sea level are neglected: wind-induced and tidal waves as well as sea level rise due to climate change are not part of this study.

3.3 Initial conditions

Sediment augmentation takes place when the river is in a morphodynamic equilibrium. This implies that the river profile has adjusted such that no changes in time take place. However, except from flow model E, the discharge varies over time and thus the equilibrium profile is changing in time. In the case study as defined in this chapter, the hydrograph belonging to a flow model is repeated every year. Therefore, the morphodynamic equilibrium is reached at a location in case the change in bed elevation at a specific moment during the year is negligibly small. In practice, the equilibrium is considered to be reached if the change in bed elevation between two consecutive years is smaller than $9e^{-6}$ m. This is in accordance with the definition of Mackin (1948), who states that a river equilibrium profile is one in which the slope has adjusted such that the flow is able to transport all the sediment load supplied from upstream.

For mixed sediment, the grain size distribution in the active layer at a location does not change if the river is in a morphodynamic equilibrium. This is an additional requirement to the equilibrium profile. In the initial situation, the grain size distribution of the substrate is equal to the grain size distribution of the sediment load from upstream.

The morphodynamic equilibrium differs per flow model and sediment case – i.e. unisize or mixed sediment. The morphodynamic equilibrium for flow model E is calculated analytically with the equations included in Appendix F.

For the flow models A, B, C and D a case-dependent simulation is run first to reach the equilibrium profile. Subsequently a new simulation starts in which the sediment measure takes place. Here, it is assumed that the differences in morphodynamic equilibrium profile between flow models A, B and C is small. Therefore, the simulations of flow models A and B use the morphodynamic equilibrium of flow model C. With this assumption, time-consuming numerical simulations - based on the implicit Preissmann scheme from Section 2.2 - are avoided.

The equilibrium profiles of flow models C, D and E for both unisize and mixed sediment are included in Appendix G. Figure 3.5 shows the grain size distribution in the active layer for the equilibrium situation of flow models C, D and E. It follows from this figure that the grain size distribution in the active layer varies over space for flow models C and D. Although not clearly visible in Figures G.1 and G.1 in Appendix G, this also applies to the bed slope. These oscillations are due to the hydrograph boundary layer, which is discussed in Section 3.4.

Figure 3.5: Grain size distribution in the active layer for the morphodynamic equilibrium of flow models C, D and E

3.4 Hydrograph boundary layer

The upstream boundary conditions are imposed 100 km from the fixed water level at the downstream end. From the equilibrium water depth during base flow in figure 3.6 it follows that the influence of the backwater curve is still significant here – i.e. the water depth has not yet reached the normal flow depth at the upstream end. This results in a flow velocity higher than the normal flow velocity during peak flow and a flow velocity lower than the normal flow velocity during base flow.

Figure 3.6: Equilibrium flow depth of flow model C during base flow compared to the normal flow depth (unysize sediment)

In Section 3.2, the sediment transport load related to flow models A and B was defined by assuming the flow depth to be the normal flow depth and further assuming an equilibrium bed slope of $1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$. Now it follows that these assumptions were not valid, the sediment transport load imposed by the upstream boundary condition will differ from the sediment transport capacity of the flow in flow models A and B. The upstream boundary conditions of flow models C, D and E were not based on their equilibrium bed slope but on the annual inflow of water and sediment in flow models A and B in Section 3.2. These upstream boundary conditions are therefore also unequal to the sediment transport capacity of the flow. This has its effects on the equilibrium profile of the river section.

Parker et al. (2007) studied the occurrence of a so-called hydrograph boundary layer in cases of an imbalance between sediment transport capacity and upstream feed of sediment. Numerical modeling was used to find out that the bed elevation varies cyclically in a short hydrograph boundary layer near the upstream end of the considered river section. Downstream of this hydrograph boundary layer the bed elevation, bed slope and bed surface grain size distribution become invariant to the hydrograph (Parker et al., 2007).

It follows from figure 3.7 that the length of the hydrograph boundary layer in the equilibrium stage for flow model C and unisize sediment is approximately equal to 45 km. Sediment augmentation takes place 75 km from the upstream end and is therefore located downstream of the hydrograph boundary layer in this situation. This implies that sediment augmentation, which is a disturbance of the equilibrium profile, will occur in a river section that is not affected by the time-dependent imbalance between the sediment transport capacity at the upstream end and the upstream boundary condition.

This is different for the mixed sediment situation. Figures 3.5 and 3.8 show that the hydrograph boundary layer still has its influence on the grain size distribution and the bed slope at the location where sediment augmentation takes place. Although the magnitude of the oscillation is much smaller than its magnitude at the upstream end, its effect has to be taken into account in the results and conclusions of this study.

Figure 3.7: The effect of the hydrograph boundary layer on the river bed slope for flow model C and unisize sediment

Figure 3.8: The effect of the hydrograph boundary layer on the river bed slope for flow model C and mixed sediment

4. Computational results

This chapter discusses the process by which the hump of sediment on the river bed, induced by one single sediment augmentation, propagates downstream. It considers adjustments in the river profile relative to the equilibrium situation. Often, this chapter considers the most downstream 30 km of the study region only, to focus on the downstream effects of sediment augmentation.

The effect of sediment augmentation on the river bed profile can be seen as a wave in the river bed, which propagates downstream and increases the bed level locally. This wave has a certain propagation velocity, the topic of Section 4.1, and it deforms over space, as discussed in Section 4.2.

4.1 Propagation velocity

This section discusses the results for unisize sediment and mixed sediment separately. The results of these two situations are compared in Chapter 7.

Unisize sediment

The propagation velocity of the wave in the river bed is closely related to the advection of sediment, because the sediment transport capacity of the flow determines how fast the sediment of the augmentation is entrained by the flow.

Figure 4.1 shows the river bed profile in the most downstream 30 km of the study region just after sediment augmentation took place and respectively one, two and three years later for flow model A. To determine the propagation velocity of the wave in the river bed, the peak of the wave is traced at various moments. This implies that the position of the wave at a certain time is defined as the position where the difference between the actual river bed profile and the equilibrium river bed profile reaches its maximum. The position of the peak is allocated to the nearest point on the grid. Therefore the accuracy of this position is limited by the spatial step of the numerical computations ($\Delta s = 200m$).

Figure 4.1: River bed profile in the first three years after sediment augmentation took place for flow model A and unisize sediment

Tracing the wave peak during 4 years after sediment augmentation took place gives insight in the propagation velocity of the peak – and more specific – during base flow and during peak flow. Figure 4.2 shows the hydrograph of flow model A (Figure 3.2 in Chapter 3), the location of the peak until it leaves the domain – i.e. where $x = 100$ km – and the propagation velocity of the wave for flow model A during 4 years after one single sediment augmentation. The horizontal axis represents the time that has passed.

The propagation velocity is computed as the first numerical derivative of the position of the peak by forward difference (Vuik et al., 2007). By definition, the forward difference of a continuously differentiable function f follows from Equation 4.1:

$$Q_f(h) = \frac{f(x+h)-f(x)}{h}, \quad h > 0 \quad [4.1]$$

The propagation velocity during peak flow is much higher than during base flow (see Figure 4.2). Furthermore, from Figure 4.2 it follows that the propagation velocity during base flow decreases over time, whereas the propagation velocity during peak flow increases every year. Table 4.1 lists the characteristic values for the propagation velocity of the wave.

Figure 4.2: Hydrograph, location of the wave in the river bed and the propagation velocity of that wave during 4 year after sediment augmentation for flow model A and unisize sediment

The increase in propagation velocity during peak flow – high peak flow as well as medium peak flow – and the decrease in propagation velocity during base flow are caused by the increasing influence of the backwater curve at locations further downstream. As a result, the sediment transport capacity of the flow increases during peak flow and decreases during base flow at locations further downstream.

Now the adjustments in the river bed profile are clear for the unsteady flow model A, the approximations based on the simplified flow models B-E are considered. Figure 4.3 shows the location of the wave for all flow models A-E as Figure 4.2 did for flow model A.

To quantify the information in Figure 4.3, Table 4.2 lists the distance travelled by the wave during half a year. The values belonging to flow models A-D are again affected by the occurrence of a backwater curve.

PROPAGATION VELOCITY OF THE WAVE		
year 1	High Peak Flow	120 m/day
	Base Flow	15 m/day
	Low Peak Flow	40 m/day
year 2	Base Flow	12 m/day
	High Peak Flow	160 m/day
	Medium Peak Flow	53 m/day
	Base Flow	10 m/day
year 3	High Peak Flow	200 m/day
	Base Flow	8 m/day
	Medium Peak Flow	80 m/day
	Base Flow	8 m/day
year 4	High Peak Flow	280 m/day
	Base Flow	5 m/day

Table 4.1: Propagation velocity of the wave in the river bed until it leaves the domain for flow model A and unisize sediment.

Figure 4.3: Location of the wave in the river bed over time (unisize sediment)

	Flow model A	Flow model B	Flow model C	Flow model D	Flow model E
year 1	6.6 km	6.4 km	6.6 km	6.4 km	7.8 km
1 st half	3.6 km	3.6 km	3.8 km	3.6 km	4.0 km
2 nd half	3.0 km	2.8 km	2.8 km	2.8 km	3.8 km
year 2	6.4 km	6.2 km	6.4 km	6.2 km	7.4 km
1 st half	3.8 km	3.6 km	4.0 km	3.8 km	3.8 km
2 nd half	2.6 km	2.6 km	2.4 km	2.4 km	3.6 km
year 3	6.0 km	5.8 km	6.0 km	5.6 km	7.4 km
1 st half	3.8 km	3.6 km	4.0 km	3.8 km	3.8 km
2 nd half	2.2 km	2.2 km	2.0 km	1.8 km	3.6 km
years 1-3	19.0 km	18.4 km	19.0 km	18.2 km	22.6 km

Table 5.2: Distance traveled by the wave during the year in the first column after sediment augmentation for all flow models in case of unisize sediment.

As discussed, the propagation velocity of the wave is influenced by the backwater curve. Since the discharge is constant for flow model E, it is possible for this flow model only to see the propagation velocity of the wave in absence of a backwater curve. From computations based on Equation 4.1, and also from the values in Table 4.2, it follows that the propagation velocity of the wave decreases slightly from 21 m/day just after sediment augmentation to 20 m/day three years later.

Mixed sediment

It was already discussed in Chapter 3 that the grain size distribution of the artificially supplied sediment is equal to the grain size distribution in the active layer at the moment sediment augmentation takes place. This implies that the fraction sand equals $F_{\text{sand}} = 0.29$ and the fraction gravel equals $F_{\text{gravel}} = 0.71$ for flow model A.

Figure 4.4 shows the increase in river bed level one year after sediment augmentation, and also the grain size distribution in the active layer at that moment. From this figure it follows that there are now two waves in the river bed, both propagating downstream. The first has a relatively high propagation velocity and the sediment in this wave is fine. The sand fraction in the active layer is $F_{\text{sand,AL}} = 0.30$ around this wave. The second wave is more slowly propagation and the active layer around this wave is coarser, $F_{\text{sand,AL}} = 0.24$. Furthermore, the slow wave is much higher than the fast wave. The fast wave reaches the end of the domain in approximately 2.5 years. The remaining part of this sections focusses on the slowly propagating wave and its effects.

Figure 4.4: A fast wave of finer sediment and a slow wave of coarser sediment in the river bed as response to a single sediment augmentation for flow model A

Figure 4.5 shows the location of the coarse wave in the river bed for all flow models until it reaches the end of the domain – i.e. where $x = 100$ km. This takes approximately 12 years for flow modes A-D (see Figure 4.5). Remarkably, the mean propagation velocity of the wave is now lower for flow model E than for all other models, whereas it was higher than all other models for unisize sediment. This is likely due to a difference in the grain size distribution in the active layer at the moment sediment augmentation takes place between flow model E and the other four flow models. This difference was already discussed in Chapter 3 (Figure 3.5). Moreover, the grain size distribution of the artificially supplied sediment is equal to that in the active layer. Appendix H discusses the results of simulations in which the grain size distribution of the supplied sediment is the same for all flow models ($F_{\text{sand}} = 0.29$ and $F_{\text{gravel}} = 0.71$), in order to find an explanation for the largely deviating propagation velocity predicted by flow model E.

Table 4.3 lists the distance travelled by the coarse wave in the 10 years after sediment augmentation took place. According to this table and Figure 4.5, flow model C gives again a better approximation of the propagation velocity as predicted by flow model A than the simplified flow models B, D and E.

Figure 4.5: Location of the wave in the river bed over time for mixed sediment (if the grain size distribution of the supplied sediment is equal to the grain size distribution in the active layer)

	Flow model A	Flow model B	Flow model C	Flow model D	Flow model E
year 1	2.0 km	2.0 km	2.2 km	2.0 km	1.4 km
year 2	2.2 km	2.2 km	2.2 km	2.2 km	1.8 km
year 3	2.2 km	2.0 km	2.2 km	2.2 km	1.6 km
year 4	2.2 km	2.2 km	2.0 km	2.0 km	1.6 km
year 5	2.2 km	2.0 km	2.2 km	2.0 km	1.4 km
year 6	2.0 km	2.0 km	2.0 km	2.0 km	1.6 km
year 7	2.0 km	1.8 km	2.0 km	2.0 km	1.6 km
year 8	2.0 km	2.0 km	2.0 km	2.0 km	1.4 km
year 9	2.0 km	1.8 km	2.0 km	1.8 km	1.6 km
year 10	2.0 km	2.0 km	1.8 km	2.0 km	1.6 km
years 1-10	20.8 km	20.0 km	20.6 km	20.2 km	15.6 km

Table 4.3: Distance traveled by the slower – and also coarser - wave during the first 10 years after sediment augmentation - for all flow models and in a river bed consisting of sand and gravel.

4.2 Deformation of the wave

Figure 4.1 already showed the decrease in height and increase in length of the wave as it propagates downstream. From the figures in Appendix I it follows that the height of the wave is not even 20% of its initial height when the hump is transferred 20 km downstream (unsize sediment). This deformation is mainly due to diffusion. Two types of characteristic values are introduced in this section, which are used to compare the deformation of the wave between different flow models. Because the results are similar for unsize and mixed sediment, this section only discusses the first. The deformation of the coarse wave for mixed sediment is included in Appendix J.

The first characteristic value to describe the shape of the wave is the height of it – i.e. the maximum distance between the bed level at a certain moment and the equilibrium bed level. Table 4.4 lists the height of the wave when it reaches the points for which the x-coordinates are respectively 80 km, 85 km, 90 km and 95 km.

	Flow model A	Flow model B	Flow model C	Flow model D	Flow model E
x = 80 km	0.227 m	0.228 m	0.226 m	0.232 m	0.220 m
x = 85 km	0.130 m	0.129 m	0.130 m	0.133 m	0.129 m
x = 90 km	0.106 m	0.091 m	0.100 m	0.100 m	0.087 m
x = 95 km	0.085 m	0.077 m	0.072 m	0.079 m	0.062 m

Table 4.4: Height of the wave at the moment it reaches the point with the given x-coordinate for all five flow models.

The second type of characteristic values are measures for the length of the wave. They are defined as the distance from the peak of the wave to the inflection points of the wave. These values may differ between the trailing edge and the leading edge of the wave – i.e. the wave is asymmetrical. These measures are similar to the standard deviation of a classical bell-shaped Gauss curve and thus denoted by $\sigma_{s,lead}$ for the leading edge of the wave and $\sigma_{s,trail}$ for the trailing edge.

Mainly due to the grid size, the information about the deformation of the wave that follows from $\sigma_{s,lead}$ and $\sigma_{s,trail}$ is limited. It gives insight in the amount of elongation of the wave, but the differences in elongation between the flow models cannot be derived from these values. Therefore, this section only discusses the values for flow model A. More information about the way in which these values are computed and the characteristic values for the other flow models are included in Appendix J.

Table 4.5 shows the characteristic values for the length of the wave at the moment it reaches the point with a certain x-coordinate. From these values it follows that the length of the wave still increases after it has travelled a distance of around 20 km, although the amount of elongation has decreased.

	$\sigma_{s,lead}$ [m]	$\sigma_{s,trail}$ [m]	$\Delta\sigma_{s,total}$ [m]
x = 80 km	1000	1400	
x = 85 km	1600	1800	1000
x = 90 km	1800	2000	400
x = 95 km	1800	2200	200

Table 4.5: Characteristic values of the wave elongation at the moment it reaches the point with the x-coordinate given in the first column for flow model A.

Appendix I presents graphically the shape of the wave at the moment it reaches the points for which $x = 80$ km, $x = 85$ km, $x = 90$ km and $x = 95$ km, for both unisize and mixed sediment and for all five flow models.

5. Application

This study focusses on the feasibility of reduced flow equations for computational modelling of sediment augmentations in lowland rivers. It follows from Chapter 4 that the adjustments in the river bed after one single sediment augmentation are approximated accurately by an alternating steady flow model with 20 modes, which is flow model C. However, the pilot study of sediment augmentation in the river Rhine near Lobith, which was introduced in Chapter 1, consists out of a repetition of several sediment augmentations. Havinga (2009) proposes a repetition time of 2 years for this specific pilot. The current chapter will provide insight in the long term effects of such a series of sediment augmentations, making use of flow model C and its underlying simplifications.

This chapter only considers the situation with mixed sediment. The initial conditions and the boundary conditions are similar to those described in Chapter 4 for flow model C and mixed sediment. The difference with previous simulations is that now a series of 10 sediment augmentations is performed. The time between two consecutive augmentations is 2 years. The remainder of this chapter considers the effects on the river bed during the series of augmentations and during the first 20 years afterwards. From Chapter 4 it follows that it takes the hump of sediment induced by one single sediment augmentation approximately 12 years to reach the end of the domain, for which $x = 100$ km.

Figure 5.1 shows the equilibrium river bed profile as well as the bed profile 15 years after the first sediment augmentation, and Figure 5.2 shows the increase in bed level at this time compared to the equilibrium situation. At this moment, eight of the series of ten sediment augmentation measures are performed. It follows from these figures that at this moment there is a significant increase in river bed level in the entire river section downstream of section where sediment augmentation is applied – i.e. the series of sediment augmentations has its effect in the entire downstream region. When two more sediment augmentations takes place, the effect in the downstream region is even larger (see Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.1: River bed level 15 years after the first sediment augmentation compared to the equilibrium river bed level

Figure 5.2: Increase in river bed level 15 years after the first sediment augmentation, when 8 of the series of 10 sediment augmentations were performed

Figure 5.3: Increase in river bed level 1 year after the series of sediment augmentations

Appendix K presents figures showing the increase in bed level compared to the equilibrium bed level during the first 20 year after the artificial sediment supply has been stopped. Moreover, this appendix considers the velocity by which the river profile returns to its equilibrium and the propagation velocity by which the wave induced by the last sediment augmentation leaves the domain.

6. Discussion

This study uses a numerical model to predict the morphodynamic behavior of a river system after sediment augmentation over a region of 1 km took place. The long-term results of the simulations are limited by the grid size and the time step that are used in the numerical model - i.e. the numerical solution of a system of differential equations approaches the analytical solution when $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ and $\Delta s \rightarrow 0$ (Cunge & Verwey, 1990). This implies that a shorter time interval Δt and a smaller spatial step Δs give more accurate results. The grid size also has a direct effect on the results as they are presented in Chapter 4. In that chapter, the location of the peak of the wave was appointed to the most nearby grid point, after which the propagation velocity of the wave was computed based on that location. The accuracy of the location of the wave, and also the accuracy of the characteristic values for the length of the wave in Chapter 4, are limited by the spatial step of $\Delta s = 200m$.

Chapter 3 explains that the sediment augmentation should take place when the river is in its morphodynamic equilibrium state in order to avoid morphodynamic adjustments induced by other processes than sediment augmentation. This equilibrium profile can only be computed analytically for flow model E (constant discharge), and therefore preliminary numerical simulations are required to find the equilibrium profile for flow models A, B, C and D. However, long-term numerical simulations based on the implicit Preissman scheme are time-consuming. Therefore, the equilibrium river profiles for flow models A and B are not computed in this study and the simulations start from the morphodynamic equilibrium of flow model C. As a result, morphodynamic adjustments that take place in these simulations may be induced by other disturbances from the morphodynamic equilibrium than sediment augmentation. Furthermore, the equilibrium profile to which the river profile recovers in the long-term may be something different from the initial profile

Another point of discussion is that the 100km domain under consideration is, for flow models A, B, C and D, affected by the occurrence of a backwater curve and a hydrograph boundary layer, although the influence of the hydrograph boundary layer is small for the situation of unisize sediment. These influences limit the applicability of the obtained results to more general cases.

While Soci (2015) determines upstream boundary conditions for which the equilibrium bed slope is the same for each flow model, the current study uses the principle that the annual inflow of water and sediment at the upstream end is the same for each flow model. This implies that the equilibrium bed slope differs between flow models. It follows from Equations 6.1 that the equilibrium bed slope influences the backwater curve.

$$d(x) = d_e + (d_0 - d_e) * 2^{\frac{x-x_0}{L_1/2}} \quad [6.1]$$

where
$$L_1/2 = 0.24 \frac{d_e}{i_b} \left(\frac{d_0}{d_e} \right)^{4/3}$$

The influence of the backwater curve on the propagation velocity of the wave during base flow and peak flow is discussed in Chapter 4. There it was found that the propagation velocity of the wave becomes higher during peak flow and lower during base flow, if the influence of the backwater curve increases. Therefore, the difference in equilibrium bed slope between the five flow models has an effect on the propagation velocity of the wave.

The upstream morphodynamic boundary conditions for mixed sediment simulations are determined based on the same principles as those for unisize sediment simulations. This implies that the annual inflow of sediment at the upstream end of the domain differs between unisize sediment simulations and mixed sediment simulations. Hence, the mean sediment transport rate differs between these two situations and this may have an effect on the propagation velocity of the wave in the river bed.

Due to the deviating grain size distribution in the active layer of flow model E compared to the other flow models, the grain size distribution of the supplied sediment is different for this flow model – i.e. the fraction sand equals $F_{\text{sand}} = 0.42$ for flow model E and $F_{\text{sand}} = 0.29$ for the other flow models. This has its effect on the propagation velocity of the wave in the river bed and on the validity of the conclusions.

The way in which the wave in the river bed deforms as it propagates downstream by the process of diffusion is discussed in Chapter 4. However, the process of diffusion also affects the shape and the height of the high water wave. Therefore, the further away the upstream boundary conditions are imposed, the lower the peak discharge at the location where sediment augmentation takes place. And according to Chapter 4, especially the peak water discharge in the river is important for the propagation of the disturbance. Diffusion of the flood wave is of no influence for flow models C, D and E since the discharge of water is continuous here.

7. Conclusions

This chapter answers the four research questions from Section 1.3. Together with the additional note included at the end of this chapter, these answers form the conclusions of this study.

What are the characteristic timescales by which the artificially supplied sediment is transported downstream and what are the effects on the river profile?

It follows from Chapter 4 that the disturbance, induced by sediment augmentation, propagates downstream as a wave in the river bed. This wave has a certain propagation velocity and it deforms in space.

In case all sediment in the river system consists of unisize grains with a diameter of 0.9 mm (very coarse sand), the wave travels 6.6 km downstream in the first year after the sediment measure. The propagation velocity of the wave depends on the discharge. During the first year, the propagation velocity during peak flow in the river ($Q_w = 5800 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$) is 120 m/day (43.8 km/year), whereas the propagation velocity during base flow ($Q_w = 2200 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$) is only 15 m/day (5.5 km/year).

The propagation velocity of the wave is largely influenced by the occurrence of a backwater curve. If a backwater curve is absent, the propagation velocity decreases slightly in time. However, if the discharge is variable a backwater curve occurs and its effect on the flow increases towards the downstream end. Since the wave propagates downstream, it reaches sections in which the water depth deviates increasingly from the normal flow depth. This increases the propagation velocity of the wave during peak flow in the river and it decreases the propagation velocity during base flow. The mean propagation velocity of the wave in the river bed during a period of one year decreases slightly.

In case the sediment in the river system consists of both sand and gravel, sediment augmentation over a river section of 1 km induces two waves in the river bed. One wave propagates faster and the sediment in this wave is finer than the sediment in the other, larger wave. The fast wave has a mean propagation speed of around 10 km/year. The mean propagation velocity of the slower wave decreases from 2.2 km/year just after sediment augmentation took place, to 2.0 km/year at the moment the wave reaches the end of the domain.

As it propagates downstream, the wave in the river bed elongates and decreases in height. The total length of the wave increases over a distance of 20 km from 1.0 km to 4.0 km. The height decreases over the same distance from 50 cm to 8.5 cm, a reduction of 83%.

What are the differences in timescales and effects on the river profile between the most accurate prediction and those predictions based on simplified flow models?

The propagation velocity of the disturbance in the river bed as predicted by an alternating steady flow model with 20 modes (flow model C in this study) approaches the propagation velocity of the disturbance predicted by an unsteady flow model (flow model A) most accurately.

In the river bed consisting of unisize sediment, the distance travelled by the disturbance in the first three years after one single sediment measure is equal for flow models A and C. For a mixed sediment river bed, flow model C predicts the travelled distance in the first ten years only 0.96 % lower. The other flow models used in this study – i.e. a quasi-steady model (flow model B), an alternating steady model with 3 modes (flow model D) and a steady model with constant discharge (flow model E) - give less accurate predictions.

The deformation of the wave in the river bed as it travels downstream, predicted by flow model C, is not exactly equal to the predictions by flow model A. However, the deviation of the characteristic values is nothing more than 1.6 % after the waves have travelled 10 km. This deviation increases to 15 % at the moment the waves have travelled 20 km downstream. The accuracy of predictions of the wave

deformation based on flow models B and D is of the same order of magnitude as based on flow model C. Predictions based on flow model E are less accurate.

To summarize, an alternating steady flow model with 20 modes gives the most accurate approximation of the morphodynamic adjustments after sediment augmentation as predicted by an unsteady flow model.

How do the adjustments in the river system change if the type of sediment changes, distinguishing unisize sediment and mixed sediment?

The sediment in the mixed sediment river bed is coarser ($F_{\text{sand}} = 0.29$) than the sediment in the unisize sediment bed ($F_{\text{sand}} = 1.0$), and so is the sediment used for sediment augmentation. This has its effect on the propagation velocity of the disturbance in the river bed: the disturbance reaches the end of the considered domain, which is $\Delta x = 25$ km away from the location of sediment augmentation, in approximately 3.75 years in a unisize river bed and the coarse wave in a mixed sediment river bed travels this distance in 12 years.

Although the grain size distribution of a real river cannot be influenced as easy as it can be done in a numerical model, the grain size distribution of the sediment used for augmentation can be adapted. This influences the time it takes for the disturbances in the river bed to leave the domain. Therefore, the coarseness of the artificially supplied sediment is a measure to influence the timescale at which a certain effect on the river bed may be achieved.

What is the long-term effect of a series of sediment measures on the river profile and how fast recovers the equilibrium profile?

Chapter 5 and Appendix K consider the effects of a series of sediment augmentations as proposed to apply in the river Rhine near Lobith (Havinga, 2009). In this application, the period between two sediment measures is two years. The long-term effect is an increased river bed level in the entire domain downstream of the location where the sediment is supplied. One year after the 10th augmentation, the increase in bed level in almost the entire downstream region is at least 10 cm.

After the series of sediment augmentations has stopped, the wave in the river bed induced by the last sediment measure leaves the domain with a propagation velocity which is approximately 5 % smaller than the propagation velocity of one single wave. Whenever this last wave in the river bed has passed a certain location, the increase in river bed level related to the equilibrium situation at that location decreases in 16 years from +6.0 cm to +3.3 cm.

Additional note

In morphodynamic modelling of river systems, an imbalance between the sediment transport capacity at the upstream end and the sediment supplied by the morphodynamic upstream boundary condition may lead to the occurrence of a hydrograph boundary layer. These oscillations in the bed elevation, bed slope and bed surface grain size distribution may have influence along the length of the hydrograph boundary layer of even more than 80 km (Figure 3.8).

8. Recommendations

It follows from the results and conclusions of this study that the morphodynamic adjustments induced by sediment augmentation can be predicted highly accurate by a simplified flow model. Although one must be aware of the limitations of these results, the use of simplified flow models makes it more attractive to use computational modelling to predict the morphodynamic behavior of a river system after sediment measures.

Future research might use the results of this study to focus on other aspects of sediment augmentation. For example, numerical models based on reduced flow equations may be used to run several simulations in which the mixture of the artificially supplied sediment varies. In this way, an ideal mixture that satisfies the objectives of a specific project may be found.

It might also be interesting to focus on the changing grain size distribution of a wave in the river bed. In this study was found that sediment augmentation by a mixture of sand and gravel induces two waves in the river bed, the one coarser than the other. It remains unknown how the grain size distribution of these waves develop while they propagate downstream. Does the coarse wave become even coarser - because the smaller particles are entrained by the flow first - or is the coarseness of the wave moderated by feeding from the active layer?

The current study has focused on sediment augmentation only 25 km upstream from a location with a fixed water level. Therefore, the influence of the occurring backwater curve on the sediment transport capacity and the propagation velocity of the wave in the river bed is significantly large. It might be interesting to focus on the propagation velocity of a disturbance in the river bed further upstream from a fixed water level. In that case, the sediment transport capacity of the flow will be less influenced by a backwater curve and one can consider how the propagation velocity of a wave in the river bed is affected by its deformation only.

Another interesting question that arises in this study deals with the differences in equilibrium river profile between flow models. In case the river bed consists of unisize sediment, the equilibrium bed slope is approximately equal for all flow models whenever the annual inflow of water and sediment at the upstream end is equal (see Figure G.1). However, in case the river bed consists of a mixture of sand and gravel, the equilibrium bed slope is higher if the discharge varies during the year than if the discharge is constant (see Figure G.2). Moreover, the grain size distribution at the bed surface depends on the variability of the discharge (see Figure 3.5). An explanation for these observations has not been found in this study.

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Appendices

Appendix A: River hydro- and morphodynamics

This appendix covers the fundamental relations describing flow, morphodynamics and sediment transport in a river system.

Flow equations

The 1D St Venant or Shallow Water equations describe the flow in a river system. These equations are derived from the Navier-Stokes equations by averaging over a characteristic period of time and by subsequently averaging over the vertical as well as the lateral direction. In fact, the equations describe the conservation of mass and momentum of the flow in a one-dimensional flow under the following assumptions (Chanson, 2004):

- the motion of water is gradually varied
- the channel bed slope is small
- the flow is considered as a one-dimensional process
- the velocity distribution over the cross-section is uniform
- the pressure is considered to be hydrostatic
- the friction slope is estimated as for the steady flow

The conservation of water mass is described by the following equation:

$$B \frac{\partial d}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q}{\partial s} = 0 \quad [A. 1]$$

where

- t = time [s]
- s = streamwise coordinate along the river [m]
- B = storage width [m]
- d = flow depth [m]
- Q = discharge [m³/s]

Equation A.1 is called the first one-dimensional St. Venant equation (Saint-Venant, 1871). Dividing all terms in Equation A.1 by the width results in the continuity equation per unit width:

$$\frac{\partial d}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial q}{\partial s} = 0 \quad [A. 2]$$

where q = water discharge per unit width [m²/s]

The conservation of streamwise momentum is described by:

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q^2}{\partial s A_c} = -g A_c \left(\frac{\partial d}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial s} \right) - c_f \frac{Q^2}{A_c R} \quad [A. 3]$$

where

- A_c = conveyance cross-section of the river [m²]
- z_b = bed level compared to a horizontal reference plane [m]
- R = hydraulic radius (R = A/P, with P the wetted perimeter) [m]
- c_f = friction coefficient [-]
- g = gravitational acceleration (= 9.81 m/s²) [m/s²]

The first term of this equation represents the local inertia term and the second term is the contribution of the advective inertia. The first term on the right hand side of this equation is the influence of gravity, which is the driving force of the flow. The second term on the right brings into account the resistance of the flow due to friction. Equation A.3 is referred to as the second one-dimensional St. Venant equation (Saint-Venant, 1871).

It must be remarked that the hydraulic radius of a river is, provided that the river width is large compared to the flow depth, approximately equal to the flow depth.

The conservation of streamwise momentum of a flow can also be represented per unit width:

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \frac{q^2}{d} = -gd \left(\frac{\partial d}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial s} \right) - c_f \left(\frac{q}{d} \right)^2 \quad [A. 4]$$

Morphodynamic response

Changes in the level of the river bed are described by the Exner equation, which considers the conservation of sediment in a river section. Neglecting the effects of lateral input of sediment along the section, the one-dimensional Exner equation is given by the following equation (Exner, 1925):

$$(1 - p)B \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q_s}{\partial x} = 0 \quad [A. 5]$$

where Q_s = sediment transport load [m^3/s]
 p = porosity of bed load material [-]

Again, the equation can be represented per unit width:

$$(1 - p) \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial q_s}{\partial x} = 0 \quad [A. 6]$$

where q_s = sediment load per unit width [m^2/s]

The Exner equation implies that the bed level does not change if the transport rate does not vary spatially.

Whereas the Exner equation describes the conservation of sediment mass for unisize sediment, the Hirano equation distinguishes different types of sediment, for example gravel and sand. The Hirano equation describes the conservation of sediment mass of one single fraction independently (Hirano, 1971):

$$c_b B \frac{\partial F_{ai} L_a}{\partial t} + c_b B F_{li} \frac{\partial z_l}{\partial t} = - \frac{\partial Q_{s,i}}{\partial x} \quad [A. 7]$$

where $z_l = z_b - L_a$

$$F_{li} = \begin{cases} F_{ai} & \text{if } \frac{\partial z_l}{\partial t} \geq 0 \\ F_{si} & \text{if } \frac{\partial z_l}{\partial t} < 0 \end{cases}$$

F_{ai} = volume fraction content of size fraction i in the active layer [-]
 F_{si} = volume fraction content of size fraction i in the substrate [-]
 F_{li} = volume fraction content of size fraction i in the interface [-]
 $Q_{s,i}$ = volume of transported sediment of size fraction i per unit time [m^3/s]
 L_a = thickness of the active layer [m]
 z_l = elevation of interface between active layer and substrate [m]

In order to use the Hirano equation, (semi-)empirical relations are necessary to determine the thickness of the active layer, the skin friction and the sediment transport load. The active layer represents the part of the bed that interacts with the flow.

The total sediment transport load of a river system with different types of sediment is given by:

$$Q_s = \sum_{i=1}^N Q_{s,i} \quad [A. 8]$$

Sediment transport relation

There are various relations by which the sediment transport load can be computed as a function of the flow velocity, but none of them is completely analytical. Therefore, the accuracy of the relation can drastically decrease if a relation is used under different conditions as under which the experiments were performed. A commonly used relation is the semi-empirical relation of Engelund-Hansen (Engelund and Hansen, 1967). This relation will also be used in this study, where the total friction experienced by the flow is assumed equal to the skin friction. Then, the sediment transport capacity is formulated by Equation A.9.

$$q_s = m u^n \quad [A. 9]$$

where $m = \frac{0.05 c_f^{\frac{3}{2}}}{(\Delta g)^2 D_{50}}$

$$n = 5$$

$$\Delta = \text{relative density } \Delta = (\rho_s - \rho_w) / \rho_w \quad [-]$$

$$D_{50} = \text{median of the particle size distribution [m]}$$

The accuracy of the relation of Engelund-Hansen is limited by the experimental range of D_{50} and θ , where D_{50} is the median grain size and θ is the dimensionless Shields parameter:

$$\theta = \frac{\tau_b}{\rho \Delta g D_{50}} = - \frac{Ri_f}{\Delta D_{50}} \quad [A. 10]$$

where $\tau_b = \rho c_f u^2$

The experiments resulting in the relation of Engelund-Hansen were in the following range:

$$0.07 < \theta < 6$$

$$0.19 \text{ mm} < D_{50} < 0.93 \text{ mm}$$

In case the sediment mixture is divided into N different grain size ranges, where each grain size range has a characteristic grain size D_i , the sediment transport capacity follows from Equations A.11 and A.12.

$$q_s = \sum_{i=1}^N q_{s,i} \quad [A. 11]$$

where $q_{s,i}$ = specific bedload transport rate of grain size fraction i [m^2/s]

$$q_{s,i} = F_{a,i} \frac{k}{D_i} u^n \quad [A. 12]$$

where $k = \frac{0.05 c_f^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\Delta^2 g^2}$

Appendix B: Steady flow

Chow (1959) defined a flow to be steady if the depth of the flow does not change during the time interval under consideration. The first St. Venant equation (Equation 2.1) then reduces to Equation B.1, which states that the specific water discharge does not vary over space.

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial s} = 0 \quad [B. 1]$$

If a constant discharge is imposed over the considered time interval, Equation 2.2 reduces to equation B.2:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \frac{q^2}{d} = -gd \left(\frac{\partial d}{\partial s} + \frac{\partial z_b}{\partial s} \right) - c_f \frac{q^2}{d^2} \quad [B. 2]$$

Combining and rewriting Equations 2.5 and 2.6 gives the backwater equation for spatially varied steady flow (Equation B.3). Here, i_f is the friction slope which is by definition equal to the loss of energy head over space.

$$\frac{\partial d}{\partial s} = \frac{i_b - i_f}{1 - Fr^2} \quad [B. 3]$$

where $Fr^2 = \frac{q_w^2}{gd^3} = \frac{u^2}{gd}$

$$i_b = -\frac{\partial z_b}{\partial s}$$

$$i_f = c_f Fr^2$$

Equation B.3 can also be written as Equation B.4, in which the dependency of the change in flow depth on the local flow depth is made more visible.

$$\frac{\partial d}{\partial s} = i_b \left(\frac{d^3 - d_e^3}{d^3 - d_g^3} \right) \quad [B. 4]$$

where $d_e^3 = \frac{c_f q_w^2}{i_b g}$

$$d_g^3 = \frac{q_w^2}{g}$$

In case $Fr^2 < 1$, the bed slope is defined to be mild and the equilibrium flow to be subcritical. A backwater curve of a river profile with a mild bed slope is called an M-type backwater curve, and three different M-types are distinguished:

- M1: The local flow depth is larger than the equilibrium flow depth and the flow depth monotonically increases in streamwise direction; the shape of the water surface profile is concave.
- M2: The local flow depth is smaller than the equilibrium flow depth but larger than the critical flow depth. In this case, the flow depth monotonically decreases in streamwise direction; the shape of the water surface profile is convex.
- M3: The local flow depth is smaller than the critical flow depth and therefore the flow is supercritical ($Fr > 1$). The flow depth increases toward the critical flow depth in streamwise direction. Since the flow in a river is in general sub-critical, an M3 backwater curve will not occur.

The type of backwater curve that will occur in a situation depends on the boundary conditions. Figure B.1 shows the three M-type backwater curves.

Figure B.1: M-type backwater curves

Appendix C: Initial hydrodynamic response for variable flow

Figures C.1 and C.2 show the backwater curves that occur in the most downstream section during respectively peak flow and base flow. Furthermore, the initial hydrodynamic response to sediment augmentation, which takes place in the section between dashed lines, follows from these figures qualitatively.

Figure C.1: Initial hydrodynamic response to sediment augmentation for peak flow

Figure C.2: Initial hydrodynamic response to sediment augmentation for base flow

Appendix D: Upstream boundary conditions of flow model C

Figure D.1: Hydrograph of flow model C (the upstream hydrodynamic boundary condition of flow model C)

Figure D.2: Sedigraph of flow model C in case of unisize sediment (the upstream morphodynamic boundary condition)

Figure D.3: Sedigraph of flow model C in case of mixed sediment (the upstream morphodynamic boundary condition)

mode	Water discharge Q_w [m ³ /s]	Unisize sediment	Mixed sediment	
		Sediment transport rate Q_s [m ³ /s]	Transport rate of sand $Q_{s,sand}$ [m ³ /s]	Transport rate of gravel $Q_{s,gravel}$ [m ³ /s]
1	2200	0.0483	0.0203	0.0050
2	2391	0.0554	0.0233	0.0058
3	2582	0.0630	0.0264	0.0066
4	2773	0.0709	0.0297	0.0074
5	2964	0.0792	0.0331	0.0083
6	3155	0.0878	0.0367	0.0093
7	3346	0.0968	0.0404	0.0102
8	3537	0.1061	0.0443	0.0112
9	3728	0.1158	0.0483	0.0123
10	3919	0.1258	0.0525	0.0133
11	4110	0.1362	0.0568	0.0145
12	4301	0.1468	0.0612	0.0156
13	4492	0.1578	0.0658	0.0168
14	4683	0.1691	0.0705	0.0180
15	4874	0.1807	0.0753	0.0193
16	5065	0.1927	0.0803	0.0205
17	5256	0.2049	0.0853	0.0219
18	5447	0.2174	0.0905	0.0232
19	5638	0.2302	0.0959	0.0246
20	5829	0.2433	0.1013	0.0260

Table D.1: List of values of water discharge and sediment transport rate for each mode, as applied for flow model C.

Appendix E: Upstream boundary conditions of flow model D

Figure E.1: Hydrograph of flow model D (the upstream hydrodynamic boundary condition of flow model D)

Figure E.2: Sedigraph of flow model C in case of unisize sediment (the upstream morphodynamic boundary condition)

Figure E.3: Sedigraph of flow model C in case of mixed sediment (the upstream morphodynamic boundary condition)

mode	Water discharge Q_w [m ³ /s]	Unisize sediment	Mixed sediment	
		Sediment transport rate Q_s [m ³ /s]	Transport rate of sand $Q_{s,sand}$ [m ³ /s]	Transport rate of gravel $Q_{s,gravel}$ [m ³ /s]
1	2200	0.0483	0.0203	0.0050
2	3865	0.1202	0.0502	0.0127
3	5946	0.2433	0.1013	0.0260

Table E.1: List of values of water discharge and sediment transport rate for each mode, as applied for flow model D.

Appendix F: Equations to obtain the equilibrium profile analytically for flow model E

The morphodynamic equilibrium for flow model E (constant discharge) and a unisize river bed can be computed analytically with equations F.1-F.3. For mixed sediment, the equations are a bit more complicated but again it is possible to determine the characteristic parameters analytically. Equations F.4-F.8 are used for these computations.

$$u_e = \left(\frac{Q_s}{Bm} \right)^{1/n} \quad [F. 1]$$

$$d_e = \frac{Q_w}{B^{1-\frac{1}{n}}} \left(\frac{m}{Q_s} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad [F. 2]$$

$$i_{be} = \frac{c_f B^{1-\frac{3}{n}}}{g Q_w} \left(\frac{Q_s}{m} \right)^{\frac{3}{n}} \quad [F. 3]$$

$$\mu = 1 - p_g + \frac{D_{gravel}}{D_{sand}} p_g \quad [F. 4]$$

where p_g = gravel fraction in the upstream load [-]

$$F_{ge} = \frac{1}{\mu} \frac{D_{gravel}}{D_{sand}} p_g \quad [F. 5]$$

where F_{ge} = gravel fraction in the active layer [-]

$$u_e = \left(\frac{D_{sand} \mu}{k} \frac{Q_{s,total}}{B} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad [F. 6]$$

$$d_e = \frac{Q_w}{B^{1-\frac{1}{n}}} \left(\frac{k}{D_{sand} \mu} \frac{1}{Q_{s,total}} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad [F. 7]$$

$$i_{be} = \frac{c_f B^{1-\frac{3}{n}}}{g Q_w} \left(\frac{D_{sand} \mu}{k} Q_{s,total} \right)^{\frac{3}{n}} \quad [F. 8]$$

Appendix G: Equilibrium river profile for flow models C, D and E

Figure G.1: Morphodynamic equilibrium profile of flow models C, D and E in the case of unisize sediment. These equilibrium profiles are the river profiles at the start of simulations in which sediment augmentation takes place

Figure G.2: Morphodynamic equilibrium profile of flow models C, D and E in the case of mixed sediment

Appendix H: Varying grain size distribution of supplied sediment

Flow model E predicts the propagation velocity of the disturbance in a mixed sediment river bed much lower than other flow models do (Figure 4.5), whereas the propagation velocity in a unisize river bed was predicted higher than by the other flow models. This appendix considers a possible explanation for this.

In Chapter 3 was found that the grain size distribution in the active layer at equilibrium differs per flow model. According to Figure 3.5, this difference between flow models C and D is negligibly small at the location where sediment augmentation takes place ($F_{\text{sand}} = 0.29$ and $F_{\text{gravel}} = 0.71$). However, the difference in grain size distribution between flow model E and the other flow models is significantly large ($F_{\text{sand}} = 0.42$ and $F_{\text{gravel}} = 0.58$). Moreover, because the grain size distribution of the artificially supplied sediment is equal to the grain size distribution in the active layer, the coarseness of the sediment used for sediment augmentation is different for flow model E. The first part of this appendix omits this difference by simulations in which the grain size distribution of the sediment used for augmentation is constant for all flow models ($F_{\text{sand}} = 0.29$ and $F_{\text{gravel}} = 0.71$). Still, the grain size distribution in the active layer differs for flow model E.

Figure H.1 shows the location of the coarse wave in the river bed, as predicted by the five flow models, in case the grain size distribution of the supplied sediment is the same in each flow model. The propagation velocity of the wave as predicted by flow model E is still smaller than the predictions by the other flow models (see Figure H.1). Therefore, the deviating grain size distribution of the supplied sediment in Chapter 4 does not explain why the results are so different to those for a unisize river bed. Other explanations may be the difference in grain size distribution in the active layer (see Figure 3.5) and, more likely, the difference in equilibrium bed slope (see Figure G.2) between flow model E and other flow models.

Figure H.1: Location of the wave in the river bed over time for mixed sediment (if the grain size distribution of the supplied sediment is the same for all flow models)

Figure H.2: Location of the wave in the river bed for two cases. The grain size distribution of the supplied sediment differs (flow model E).

Now, two different sediment augmentations are applied under the same flow conditions and in the same equilibrium river profile. The only difference is the grain size distribution of the supplied sediment; the one is coarser ($F_{\text{sand}} = 0.29$) than the other ($F_{\text{sand}} = 0.42$). The difference in propagation velocity of the wave induced by the different composition of sediment augmentation is small (see Figure H.2).

In Chapter 4 was found that sediment augmentation in a river bed consisting of sand and gravel particles induces two different waves in the river bed. The first wave propagates relatively fast and transfers finer sediment than the second wave (see Figure 4.4). The ratio between the magnitudes of the fast and the slowly propagating wave – i.e. their height and length - depends on the grain size distribution of the supplied sediment (see Figures H.3 and H.5). According to Figures H.4 and H.6, the fine wave moderates the coarseness of the main disturbance in the river bed.

Figure H.3: Increase in river bed level for two different augmentations after 1 year (predictions by flow model E)

Figure H.4: Grain size distribution in the active layer for two different augmentations after 1 year

Figure H.5: Increase in river bed level for two different augmentations after 2 years (predictions by flow model E)

Figure H.6: Grain size distribution in the active layer for two different augmentations after 2 years

Appendix I: Deformation of the wave (figures)

The Figures J.1-J.4 show the shape of the wave at the moment it reaches the points for which respectively $x = 80$ km, $x = 85$ km, $x = 90$ km and $x = 95$ km in the situation of unisize sediment. All flow models are included in these figures. The Figures J.5-J.6 do the same for the coarse wave of mixed sediment.

Figure J.1: Shape of the wave in the river bed when it reaches the point for which $x = 80$ km (unsize sediment)

Figure J.2: Shape of the wave in the river bed when it reaches the point for which $x = 85$ km (unsize sediment)

Figure J.3: Shape of the wave in the river bed when it reaches the point for which $x = 90$ km (unisize sediment)

Figure J.4: Shape of the wave in the river bed when it reaches the point for which $x = 90$ km (unisize sediment)

Figure J.5: Shape of the wave in the river bed when it reaches the point for which $x = 80$ km (mixed sediment)

Figure J.6: Shape of the wave in the river bed when it reaches the point for which $x = 85$ km (mixed sediment)

Figure J.7: Shape of the wave in the river bed when it reaches the point for which $x = 90$ km (mixed sediment)

Figure J.8: Shape of the wave in the river bed when it reaches the point for which $x = 95$ km (mixed sediment)

Appendix J: Deformation of the wave (complement)

Section 4.2 introduces the characteristic values $\sigma_{s,lead}$ and $\sigma_{s,trail}$ as a measure to quantify the elongation of the wave. This appendix explains how these values are defined. Furthermore, it lists these characteristic values for all flow models and for both unisize and mixed sediment, whereas Section 4.2 only discusses the values for flow model A and unisize sediment.

The two characteristic values $\sigma_{s,lead}$ and $\sigma_{s,trail}$ are defined as the distances the peak to the inflection points of the peak. The distance from the peak to the inflection point on the leading edge is $\sigma_{s,lead}$ and to the inflection point on the trailing edge is $\sigma_{s,trail}$.

Equation J.1 gives a numerical approximation of the second derivative of a continuously differentiable function f (Vuik et al., 2007):

$$f''(x) \approx Q(h) = \frac{f(x+h) - 2f(x) + f(x-h)}{h^2} \quad [J.1]$$

The underlying function of the bed level increase is unknown, but Equation J.1 can still be used since the function values are known for each grid point ($\Delta s = h = 200 \text{ m}$). By definition, the second derivative of the curve equals zero at the locations of inflection points. Therefore, the locations of the inflection points are found by equating Equation J.1 to zero. Figure J.1 shows the definition of $\sigma_{s,lead}$ and $\sigma_{s,trail}$ graphically.

Figure J.1: Definition of $\sigma_{s,lead}$ and $\sigma_{s,trail}$ in this study

These characteristic values are computed for the wave at the moment it reaches a certain x-coordinate in the domain. Table J.1 presents the values for all flow models and unisize sediment for respectively $x = 80 \text{ km}$, $x = 85 \text{ km}$, $x = 90 \text{ km}$ and $x = 95 \text{ km}$. Table J.3 lists the characteristic values of the slow - and coarse - wave for mixed sediment. Tables J.2 and J.4 list the height of the wave at a certain location for respectively unisize and mixed sediment.

	Flow model A		Flow model B		Flow model C		Flow model D		Flow model E	
	$\sigma_{s,lead}$	$\sigma_{s,trail}$								
x = 80 km	1000	1400	1000	1400	1000	1400	1000	1400	1000	1400
x = 85 km	1600	1800	1600	1800	1600	1800	1400	1800	1400	1800
x = 90 km	1800	1800	2000	2000	1600	2000	1800	1800	1800	2200
x = 95 km	1800	2200	1800	2200	1800	2200	2000	2000	2200	2400

Table J.1: Characteristic values of the wave length at the moment it reaches a certain x-coordinate (unysize sediment).

	Flow model A	Flow model B	Flow model C	Flow model D	Flow model E
x = 80 km	0.227 m	0.228 m	0.226 m	0.232 m	0.220 m
x = 85 km	0.130 m	0.129 m	0.130 m	0.133 m	0.129 m
x = 90 km	0.106 m	0.091 m	0.100 m	0.100 m	0.087 m
x = 95 km	0.085 m	0.077 m	0.072 m	0.079 m	0.062 m

Table J.2: Height of the wave at the moment it reaches a certain x-coordinate (unysize sediment).

	Flow model A		Flow model B		Flow model C		Flow model D		Flow model E	
	$\sigma_{s,lead}$	$\sigma_{s,trail}$								
x = 80 km	1000	1400	1000	1400	1000	1400	1000	1400	1000	1400
x = 85 km	1400	1800	1600	1800	1400	1800	1600	1800	1400	1800
x = 90 km	1800	2200	1800	2200	1800	2200	1800	2200	1800	2200
x = 95 km	2200	2200	2000	2400	2000	2200	2200	2400	2200	2400

Table J.3: Characteristic values of the wave length at the moment it reaches a certain x-coordinate (mixed sediment).

	Flow model A	Flow model B	Flow model C	Flow model D	Flow model E
x = 80 km	0.200 m	0.204 m	0.199 m	0.204 m	0.168 m
x = 85 km	0.125 m	0.126 m	0.123 m	0.127 m	0.104 m
x = 90 km	0.092 m	0.089 m	0.087 m	0.087 m	0.074 m
x = 95 km	0.071 m	0.064 m	0.066 m	0.071 m	0.057 m

Table J.4: Height of the wave at the moment it reaches a certain x-coordinate (mixed sediment).

Appendix K: Long-term effects of a series of sediment augmentations

This appendix focusses on the process by which the surplus sediment is transported out of the domain and the velocity by which the equilibrium profile recovers. This appendix is a complement on Chapter 5 in the main document, in which the series of sediment augmentations was already introduced. Many figures are included in this appendix to present the long-term effects of the series of sediment augmentations properly.

Figures K.1-K.10 show the increase in river bed level during 19 years after artificial sediment supply stopped: Figure K1 shows the effect one year after the last sediment augmentation and every other figure that succeeds shows the effect 2 years later.

This appendix discusses 2 characteristic velocities. The first is the velocity by which the river bed lowers at the location where the sediment augmentations take place ($x = 75$ km). The second is the propagation velocity of the peak of the last wave – i.e. the peak of the wave induced by the 10th sediment augmentation.

Table K.1 lists the difference between the bed level and the equilibrium bed level (denoted by Δz_b) at the location where the sediment augmentation takes place ($x = 75$ km) and at a certain time after the last sediment augmentation. Also, it lists the mean velocity by which the bed level lowers during a time interval. It follows from this table that the velocity by which the bed level lowers decreases if the bed level is closer to the equilibrium bed level and if the peak of the wave has travelled downstream far enough to neglect the influence of its tail.

Table K.2 lists the location of the wave induced by the 10th sediment augmentation at a certain time after that augmentation, and also the mean propagation velocity during the time intervals. This table is similar to Table 4.3 for one single sediment augmentation. According to Table K.2, the propagation speed of the last wave of a series of augmentations is something lower than the propagation speed of the wave induced by one single sediment augmentation (approximately 5 %).

Time after last sediment augmentation	Δz_b [mm]	$\Delta z_b / \Delta t$ [mm/year]
1 year	59.6	+ 0.35
3 years	60.3	- 1.10
5 years	58.1	- 1.65
7 years	54.8	- 1.95
9 years	50.9	- 2.00
11 years	46.9	- 2.00
13 years	42.9	- 1.90
15 years	39.1	- 1.75
17 years	35.6	- 1.45
19 years	32.7	

Table K.1: Difference between the river bed level and the equilibrium bed level and the mean rate by which this difference changes at the location of sediment augmentation ($x = 75$ km).

Time after last sediment augmentation	Location of peak of the wave [km]	Mean propagation velocity [km/year]
1 year	77.8	1.9
3 years	81.6	1.9
5 years	85.4	2.0
7 years	89.4	1.9
9 years	93.2	1.8
11 years	96.8	

Table K.2: Location of the wave induced by the 10th sediment augmentation and the mean propagation velocity of that wave.

Figure K.1: Increase in river bed level 1 year after the series of sediment augmentations

Figure K.2: Increase in river bed level 3 years after the series of sediment augmentations

Figure K.3: Increase in river bed level 5 years after the series of sediment augmentations

Figure K.4: Increase in river bed level 7 years after the series of sediment augmentations

Figure K.5: Increase in river bed level 9 years after the series of sediment augmentations

Figure K.6: Increase in river bed level 11 years after the series of sediment augmentations

Figure K.7: Increase in river bed level 13 years after the series of sediment augmentations

Figure K.8: Increase in river bed level 15 years after the series of sediment augmentations

Figure K.9: Increase in river bed level 17 years after the series of sediment augmentations

Figure K.10: Increase in river bed level 19 years after the series of sediment augmentations